

Ethnomedicinal Information and Phytochemical Screening of Medicinal Plants Used in the Treatment of Diarrhea in Lagos State, Nigeria

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between both authors. Author OJS designed the work, wrote the protocols and supervised author OSO, who carried out the ethnobotanical survey, phytochemical screenings and wrote the manuscript. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

Aim: To identify and screen the phytochemicals of medicinal plants with anti-diarrhea potential in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Place and Duration of the Study: Ethnobotanical survey and phytochemical screenings of plants used in traditional medicine for the treatment of diarrhea in Nigeria were carried out between April and November, 2014.

Methodology: Ethnobotanical survey of medicinal plants used for the treatment of diarrhea in Lagos State, Nigeria was carried out using oral interviews (without questionnaire) method to gather information from herb sellers in major herbal markets in Lagos State. The qualitative phytochemical screenings of the identified medicinal plants was carried out using standard screening procedures.

Results: Twenty-five plant species belonging to 16 families were identified. The families *Asteraceae*, *Lamiaceae* and *Combretaceae* have the highest number of plant species followed by the family *Fabaceae*. *Aristolochia albida*, *Parinari curatellifolia*, *Acanthospermum hispidum*, *Phyllanthus amarus* and *Gongronema latifolium* were the most frequently mentioned and highly

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recommended of all the species. The plant parts used for the treatment are the leaves, bark and roots which were prepared by infusion, decoction or taken in powdered form. Majority of the plants are taken orally. The phytochemical screening revealed the presence of alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, cardiac glycoside, anthraquinones and phlobatannins.

Keywords: Ethnobotanical survey; medicinal plants; phytochemicals; diarrhea.

1. INTRODUCTION

Diarrhea is defined by the World Health Organization as having three or more loose or liquid stools per day, or as having more stools than is normal for a person. It is a serious health problem worldwide and causes 4% of all deaths [1]. Billion of cases of diarrhea occur per year [2]. It is most common in developing countries notably Africa, where young children get diarrhea on average of three times a year [1,3]. Diarrhea remains the second leading cause of infant mortality (16%) after pneumonia (17%) in this age group [4]. It was reported worldwide in 2004 that approximately 2.5 billion cases of diarrhea occurred which results in 1.5 million deaths among children under the age of five [1]. The most serious danger posed by diarrhea is dehydration [5]. Dehydration caused by diarrhea is one of the biggest single killers of children in the modern world and diarrhea itself is one of the major causes of nutritional loss and poor growth [1]. Dehydration occurs when lost body fluids and electrolytes are not replaced and death can follow severe dehydration [5]. During a diarrheal episode, water and electrolytes (sodium, chloride, potassium and bicarbonate) are lost through liquid stools, vomit, sweat, urine and breathing. Although anyone can become dehydrated, those who become dehydrated the most easily are babies under a year old, the elderly, anyone who has a fever and people in hot climates [6]. Diarrhea and vomiting are more serious in babies than older children because babies can easily lose too much fluid from their bodies and become dehydrated [1].

The most common cause of diarrhea is gastrointestinal infections [1]. Viral infection of the guts which is the most common cause of diarrhea last for two days and is sometimes called "intestinal flu" [7,8]. Diarrhea may also be caused by bacterial infection (the cause of most types of food poisoning). Other causes may be as a result of infections by other organisms, eating foods that upset the digestive system,

allergies to certain foods and many more [9]. Symptoms of diarrhea can be broken down into uncomplicated (or non-serious) diarrhea and complicated diarrhea. Complicated diarrhea may be a sign of a more serious illness and symptoms such as blood mucus, weight loss, and fever are seen [1]. Symptoms of uncomplicated diarrhea include abdominal bloating or cramps, thin or loose stools, watery stool, sense of urgency to have a bowel movement, nausea and vomiting [9].

Lagos State, which is the study area is located in the south western part of Nigeria. It lies at latitude 6.45° N and longitude 3.39° E. It has an elevation of 10 meters above sea level and 22% of its 3,577 km square are lagoons and creek. Diarrhea is one of the main causes of high mortality rate in Lagos State, where several numbers of children under the age of five die annually from severe diarrheal diseases. This is due to crowded living conditions and poor hygiene, which are typical of Lagos State.

Several studies have shown that medicinal plant can be effective in the treatment of diarrhea. [10] worked on fifty (50) plants used for treatment of dysentery and diarrhea by the Bhoxa community in India. [11] conducted ethnobotanical survey of plants used to treat diarrhea in the Limpopo Province of South Africa. A total of 20 plant species representing 16 families and 20 genera were found to be commonly used by the Bapedi traditional healers to treat and manage diarrhea in the Province.

Although, Oral Rehydration Therapy (ORT) and the use of antibiotics in some cases have been helpful in the treatment of diarrheal diseases, numerous medicinal plants with anti-diarrhea potential have not been applauded by many Nigerians. This research therefore, focuses on the identification and preliminary phytochemical screenings of the medicinal plants used in traditional medicine for the treatment of diarrhea in Nigeria.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Ethnomedicinal Information

Information on plants used in traditional medicine for the treatment of diarrhea in Nigeria was collected between April and November, 2014. This was done by using oral interview method to gather information from forty (40) herb sellers in four large herbal markets (Iyana- Iba, Ikorodu, Agege and Mushin) in Lagos State. Also, ten (10) herbal medicine practitioners as well as ten (10) local herbalists from rural areas of Lagos State were interviewed. Information collected included local names, the parts of plants used, method of administration and the dosages of the medicinal herbs. The plants were initially identified by their local names and were later properly identified and authenticated by Dr (Mrs) O.J Sharaibi, a Taxonomist in the Department of Botany, Lagos State University. Voucher specimens (LSH/540/014) of the plants were deposited in the Lagos University Herbarium for future reference.

2.2 Plant Collection

Fresh leaves of the medicinal plants used for the phytochemical screenings were collected from Badagry, Oko-afu, Ikorodu and Igando areas of Lagos State, Nigeria.

2.3 Sample Preparation

All the fresh plant materials were carefully rinsed under running water, air dried and later pulverized before extraction.

2.4 Aqueous Extraction

Two Hundred grams of each powdered plant material were soaked in 1000 ml distilled water for 48 hours at 30°C on an orbital shaker (Stuart Scientific Orbital Shaker, UK). The extract was filtered by Whatman no.1 paper. The filtrate was freeze dried using Savant Refrigerated Vapor Trap (RTV 4104, USA). The freeze-dried extract was stored at 4°C before bioassay.

2.5 Ethanol Extraction

Two Hundred grams of the samples were Soxhlet's extracted using 250 ml of 95% ethanol. The extraction lasted for 6 hours. The obtained extracts were further evaporated to dryness using the vacuum rotary evaporator machine.

2.6 Phytochemical Screening

The plant samples were screened for tannins flavonoids, phlobatannins, saponins, alkaloids, anthraquinones and cardiac glycosides using standard procedures by [12,13] and [14].

3. RESULTS

Twenty five (25) plant species belonging to sixteen (16) families were identified for the treatment of diarrhea in Lagos State, Nigeria as shown in Table 1.

3.1 Phytochemical Screening

The plant samples screened contain tannins, flavonoids, saponins, alkaloids anthraquinones and cardiac glycosides while phlobatannins was present only in *Cnestis ferruginea* as shown in Table 2.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Twenty-five (25) plant species belonging to sixteen (16) families were identified for the treatment of diarrhea (Table 1). The most frequently mentioned and highly recommended were *Aristolochia albida*, *Parinari curatellifolia*, *Acanthospermum hispidum*, *Phyllanthus amarus* and *Gongronema latifolium*. Plant parts used were the leaves, bark, roots, fruits and seeds. The most commonly reported plant part used were leaves followed by the bark while the root was the least of the plant part used. Infusion was the most commonly (52%) used method of preparation followed by decoction while grinding into powder form was the least mentioned method. The medicinal plants are taken orally. The preliminary screenings of the medicinal plants used in folklores for the treatment of Diarrhea in Lagos, Nigeria revealed the presence of many important phytochemicals such as alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, cardiac glycosides, anthraquinones, phlobatannins etc. that are of therapeutic effects.

All the medicinal plants contain alkaloids, tannins and flavonoids. Cardiac glycosides were present in all plants except *Boerhavia coccinea*, *Alchornea cordifolia*, *Psidium guajava* and *Pteleopsis suberosa*. Anthraquinone was present in all plant except in *Alchornea cordifolia*, *Nauclea diderrichi*, *Psidium guajava*, *Boerhavia coccinea*, *Tetrapleura tetraptera* and *Pentaclethra macrophylla*. Phlobatannins was very rare among the plants investigated and was seen only in *Cnestis ferruginea*.

Table 1. Plants used for the treatment of Diarrhea in Lagos State, Nigeria

Scientific name	Family	Yoruba name	Parts used	Preparation	Dosage
<i>Gongronema latifolium</i> Benth.	Asclepiaceae	Madunmaro	Leaf	Cooked	1 glass cup daily
<i>Acanthospermum hispidum</i> DC	Asteraceae	Dagunro	Leaf	Infusion	2 glass cups daily
<i>Terminalia ivorensis</i> A. chev	Combretaceae	Afara dudu	Leaf	Infusion	1 glass cup (50ml)
<i>Gmelina arborea</i> Roxb	Lamiaceae	Igi melina	Leaf	Infusion	2 glass cups a day
<i>Aristolochia albida</i> Duch	Aristolochiaceae	Akogun	Leaf	Infusion	2 glass cups daily
<i>Parkia bicolor</i> A. chev	Fabaceae	Igba odo	Stem	Decoction	2 glass cups daily
<i>Anogeissus leiocarpus</i> DC	Combretaceae	Orin- odan	bark	Decoction	1 glass cup daily
<i>Alchornea cordifolia</i> Sch.& Th	Euphorbiaceae	Ipa	Stem	Infusion	2 glass cups daily
<i>Cnestis ferruginea</i> Vahl. DC	Connaraceae	Afundanyin	bark	Decoction	2 to 3 glass cups a day
<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> Linn	Asteraceae	Imi esu	Leaf	Infusion	2 glass cups a day
<i>Nauclea diderrichi</i> DW	Rubiaceae	Opepe	Root	Decoction	2 to 3 glass cups daily
<i>Psidium guajava</i> Linn	Myrtaceae	Gilova	Leaf	Infusion	2 glass cups daily
<i>Chromolaena odorata</i> Linn	Asteraceae	Ewe Awolowo	Root	Infusion	2 glass cups daily
<i>Boerhavia coccinea</i> ; Mill	Nyctaginaceae	Atipa	Leaf	Infusion	2 glass cups daily
<i>Vitellaria paradoxa</i> C.F. Gaertn	Sapotaceae	Ori oyo	Stem bark	Decoction	2 glass cups daily
<i>Ficus exasperata</i> Vahl	Moraceae	Ipin	Seed, leaf	Infusion and decoction	2 glass cups daily
<i>Vitex doniana</i> Linn	Lamiaceae	Ori nla	Seed	Infusion	2 glass cups daily
<i>Bryophyllum pinnatum</i> Linn	Crassulaceae	Abamoda	seed and nut	Infusion	1 to 2 glass cup daily
<i>Ocimum sanctum</i> Linn	Lamiaceae	Efinrin- ajase	Leaf	Leaf juice	About 25ml of extract
<i>Tetrapleura tetraptera</i> Taub	Mimosaceae	Aidan	Seed and fruit	Decoction	2 to 3 glass cups daily
<i>Parinari curatellifolia</i> Benth	Rosaceae	Abere	Leaf	Decoction	1 glass cup daily
<i>Pteleopsis suberosa</i> Eng. & Diel	Combretaceae	Okuku	Leaf	Decoction or powder	2 to 3 glass cups daily
<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> Linn	Euphorbiaceae	Dobisowo	Stem bark	Decoction	2 glass cups daily

Table 2. Phytochemical screening of medicinal plants used in the treatment of Diarrhea in Lagos State, Nigeria

Medicinal plants	ALK	FLA	TAN	GLY	ANTH	PHLO	SAP
<i>Gongronema latifolium</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
<i>Acanthospermum hispidum</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
<i>Terminalia ivorensis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
<i>Aristolochia albida</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Parkia bicolor</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
<i>Anogeissus leiocarpus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
<i>Alchornea cordifolia</i>	+	+	+	-	-	-	-
<i>Cnestis ferruginea</i>	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
<i>Nauclea diderrichi</i>	+	+	+	+	-	-	+
<i>Psidium guajava</i>	+	+	+	-	-	-	+
<i>Chromolaena odorata</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
<i>Boerhavia coccinea</i>	+	+	+	-	-	-	+
<i>Pentaclethra macrophylla</i>	+	+	+	+	-	-	+
<i>Acacia nilotica</i>	+	+	+	+	-	-	+
<i>Vitellaria paradoxa</i>	+	+	+	+	-	-	+
<i>Vitex doniana</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
<i>Ficus exasperata</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
<i>Bryophyllum pinnatum</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
<i>Tetrapleura tetraptera</i>	+	+	+	+	-	-	+
<i>Parinari curatellifolia</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
<i>Pteleopsis suberosa</i>	+	+	+	-	-	-	+
<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	-

ALK=Alkaloids; FLA= Flavonoids; TAN=Tannins; GLY=Glycosides; ANTH=Anthraquinones; PHLO=Phlobatannins

These compounds (secondary metabolites) are known to exhibit pharmacological activity and support good health [15]. Recently several flavonoids have been shown to inhibit biofilm formation of *E. coli* [16]. It has been reported that phyloretin, a flavonoid, possesses anti-inflammatory effect against Inflammatory Bowel Diseases (IBDs) *in vitro* [17]. The anti-diarrheal activity of the flavonoids has been ascribed to their ability to inhibit intestinal mobility and hydro electric secretion [18]. Flavonoids are involved in scavenging the oxygen derived from free radicals [19]. It has also been established that flavonoids from medicinal plants possess high antioxidant potential due to their hydroxyl groups and protect humans more efficiently against any free radical related diseases [20,21]. Flavonoids are also presumed to be responsible for inhibitory effect exerted upon several enzymes including those involved in the arachidonic acid metabolism. Alkaloids are the most therapeutically significant plant substances and are used as basic medical agents because of their analgesic and antibacterial properties [22]. Tannins are useful in the treatment of intestinal disorders such as

diarrhea, dysentery and urinary tract infections thus exhibiting anti microbial activity [23,24]. The presence of tannins was found to play a major role in anti fungal, anti bacterial, astringent and anti biotic activities [25]. It has also been reported that cardiac glycosides has antispasmodic properties and act as good sedatives [26]. Anthraquinone glycoside has the property of being hydrolysed by enzyme and used medicinally as indigation [27]. Phlobatannins have also being reported to have specific action on the coronary circulation [28]. These phytochemicals present in the plants could be responsible for the activity of the plants in the management of diarrhea.

4.1 Conclusion

This study identified indigenous medicinal plants that can be effective in the treatment of diarrhea. The plants contained phytochemicals that have high therapeutic activities. Further studies on these plants may yield effective drugs that can help combat diarrhea.

CONSENT

It is not applicable.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

It is not applicable.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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